

Original article

Cooperative transportation using rotorcraft: Swing state estimation and control

Elia Costantini

University of Bologna, Department of Industrial Engineering (DIN), CIRI Aerospace, Forlì, 47121, Italy

ARTICLE INFO

Communicated by Christian Circi

ABSTRACT

A cooperative transportation scenario is examined wherein two rotorcraft jointly carry a suspended payload. The equations of motion are first derived using the Lagrangian approach, under the assumption that the coupled slung-load system is represented by three point masses connected via two massless, rigid cables. The system is identified as underactuated, with a remaining degree of freedom corresponding to the swinging motion of the payload. An observation model is then formulated, enabling direct estimation of the oscillation angle from a minimal set of measurements, specifically the positions of both rotorcraft and their accelerations in the local horizontal plane. Data fusion is achieved through the application of a Fading Gaussian Deterministic Filter, the theoretical foundations of which were recently investigated by one of the authors. The proposed methodology is numerically validated in a high-fidelity simulation environment, where the multirotors are modeled as rigid bodies, accounting for viscous-elastic cable dynamics, aerodynamic disturbances, and rotor forces and moments computed via Blade Element Theory. The estimated swing angle and its rate are demonstrated to serve as effective feedback variables for payload stabilization. To this end, a control strategy is introduced to achieve simultaneous minimal-swing formation-keeping and trajectory-tracking maneuvers, offering improved flight characteristics and reduced overall energy consumption.

1. Introduction

In aerial delivery operations, two principal methods are commonly employed [1]: the payload may be either rigidly affixed to the vehicle or suspended via a cable. The rigid attachment approach is the most prevalent, typically realized through the use of clamps or by leveraging a sufficiently large fuselage. However, this solution often results in increased take-off weight and may be unsuitable for transporting large payloads or for missions requiring aerial delivery where landing is not feasible [2,3]. Alternatively, suspended payload configurations offer the advantage of enabling aerial delivery without the need to land, thereby enhancing mission efficiency while preserving rotorcraft performance and system simplicity. Nevertheless, the introduction of a suspended mass generates disturbance forces and moments that significantly influence the dynamics of the carrier platform, rendering the system underactuated and challenging to control. Moreover, the resulting oscillations can pose risks to both the payload and surrounding infrastructure due to potential collisions [4].

While the use of a single aerial vehicle may suffice for certain applications, a range of transportation tasks, such as lifting payloads exceeding the capacity of a single rotorcraft or maintaining functionality in the event of vehicle failure, necessitate the use of cooperative multi-agent systems. Consequently, cooperative payload transportation has garnered considerable attention in the literature. Depending on the adopted control strategy, cable-suspended cooperative transportation methods are typically categorized into two frameworks: UAV-based (decentralized) and payload-based (centralized). In both approaches, the stabilization of payload oscillations is of paramount importance, and many proposed solutions draw inspiration from the field of overhead crane control [5].

In decentralized frameworks [6–10], primary emphasis is placed on maintaining UAV formation, treating payload swing as a perturbation that complicates position control. For instance, [6] proposes a passivity-based formation control strategy, demonstrating that the system admits a continuum of equilibria and proving stability for all configurations in which the cables remain taut. In [7], payload mass is assumed to be unknown and the formation is subjected to wind disturbances. The control

* Corresponding author.

E-mail addresses: costantini3@unibo.it (E. Costantini), emanuele.deangelis4@unibo.it (E.L. de Angelis), fabrizio.giulietti@unibo.it (F. Giulietti).

design is supported by a Lyapunov-based analysis, and its performance is validated through simulations and field experiments. A Lyapunov-based controller for aerial co-manipulation with two UAVs is presented in [8], while [9] employs a nonlinear control strategy based on feedback linearization to enable trajectory tracking, swing mitigation, and obstacle avoidance in a two-UAV formation. In [10], the authors propose a controller capable of achieving simultaneous trajectory tracking, formation maintenance, and swing suppression for a system modeled as three point masses connected via two linear-elastic cables. Theoretical guarantees of local exponential stability are provided under the assumption of a two-time-scale behavior: fast dynamics govern formation and swing stabilization, while slow dynamics describe trajectory tracking.

In centralized architectures [11–15], the primary objective is precise trajectory tracking of the payload, considering the full dynamic coupling among system components. This coupling introduces substantial challenges for control design. For example, [11] adopts a modeling approach rooted in the theory of reconfigurable cable-driven parallel robots, addressing full system dynamics. A multi-objective controller for trajectory tracking, formation keeping, and collision avoidance is proposed in [12], employing two helicopters to transport a point-mass payload. In [13], a sub-optimal LQR-PID controller is introduced to minimize swing by aligning the velocities of the payload and UAVs in a designated formation. A hierarchical approach is taken in [14], wherein the payload, considered the leader, computes the net force and torque required to follow a trajectory, and a tension-distribution problem is solved using sequential least-squares programming. In [15], a reinforcement learning framework is explored, combining centralized training and decentralized execution with a reward function that integrates both positive and negative reinforcements.

Accurate estimation of payload's position relative to the formation is critical for effective anti-sway control. Various sensing strategies have been proposed in the literature, with optical feedback systems being particularly common. These often involve motion capture devices, which, while highly accurate, are associated with increased complexity, cost, and limited practicality in operational environments [16]. An alternative is the use of onboard vision systems, though they introduce drawbacks such as increased weight, power demand, computational load, and susceptibility to environmental variability [17,18]. Non-optical solutions have also been explored, including the use of inclinometers attached to the payload [19], and potentiometers installed on the vehicle to measure appendage orientations in aerial manipulation tasks [20]. High-precision GNSS-based methods are also feasible, provided that both the payload and vehicles are equipped with dedicated receivers [21].

With respect to the estimation algorithms, different methods have been evaluated in the past, each offering different trade-offs in terms of computational complexity, robustness to disturbances, and sensor requirements. The Extended Kalman Filter (EKF) has been among the most commonly adopted techniques, owing to its simplicity and effectiveness in nonlinear systems. Some of the authors of the present work have developed a nonlinear EKF [22] that relies solely on onboard IMU measurements to estimate swing angles and cable forces, while compensating for external aerodynamic disturbances such as wind. Such an approach is validated in both simulation and experimental flight tests, demonstrating improved robustness and energy efficiency. In parallel, other researchers have employed the Unscented Kalman Filter (UKF) to better capture the effects of nonlinearities and sensor noise, especially in dynamic transport scenarios [23]. In such a case, the UKF has been combined with adaptive schemes, allowing real-time tuning of noise covariances to accommodate changing flight conditions. To enhance robustness in the presence of bounded disturbances and model uncertainties, some works have implemented zonotopic state estimators. In [24] this approach has been applied to estimate the position and orientation of suspended loads, integrating the estimator within a discrete-time state-feedback mixed H_2/H_∞ control scheme. Results have confirmed strong performance under limited a priori knowledge of disturbances, albeit

with increased computational requirements. More recently, researchers have integrated estimation and control within perception-aware frameworks. Li et al. [25] have proposed a Perception-Constrained Model Predictive Control (PCMPC) architecture that fuses monocular vision and IMU data to estimate cable dynamics at high frequency, while ensuring visibility constraints are maintained. This approach has achieved precise trajectory tracking in visually constrained environments while reducing onboard computational burden and preserving estimation accuracy in cluttered or occluded scenes. Although less explored in this specific context, Moving Horizon Estimation (MHE) has also been recognized as a powerful tool for managing nonlinearities and constraints. While MHE has been successfully applied in related UAV applications, its adoption in suspended-load transport scenarios has remained limited, primarily due to its computational cost and implementation complexity. However, recent advancements in embedded optimization solvers and parallelized MHE implementations have begun to make real-time application more feasible, particularly for systems with short prediction horizons [26]. Complementary to model-based approaches, researchers have also explored learning-based estimation. In [27] a learning-based hybrid model is presented that combines first-principle dynamics with a neural predictor that captures unmodeled residual forces/torques, stemming from payload dynamics, for multirotor UAVs. The hybrid model is integrated into an MPC framework and is validated both in simulations and real-world experiments. Results show significant reduction in force/torque estimation errors, if compared to pure learning-based estimators where neural networks or hybrid physics-informed models have been trained to infer load dynamics from flight data. Although these methods have demonstrated potential in capturing unmodeled dynamics and compensating for sensor delays, challenges related to their generalizability and safety assurance remain unresolved, limiting their current applicability in safety-critical aerial systems.

This study introduces a novel method for estimating the swing state of a payload suspended and transported cooperatively by two rotorcraft. The coupled slung-load system is first modeled using the Lagrangian formulation, with a tailored parameterization of payload position that captures its oscillatory dynamics. The resulting system is shown to be underactuated. Linearization is performed about the hovering equilibrium with the payload at rest. An observation algorithm is then developed to infer the swing angle and its rate based solely on measurements of vehicle acceleration in the horizontal plane. The estimation task is approached via the Fading Gaussian Deterministic Filter (FGDF), a technique offering optimal configuration tuning to minimize estimation error in the presence of model uncertainties and measurement noise. Within this framework, the filter provides globally optimal performance within its class, as detailed in [28,29].

The estimated swing states are subsequently employed within a proportional feedback controller designed to stabilize payload oscillations in a decentralized manner. The controller structure builds on the framework introduced in [5], and is conceived as a modular addition to existing rotorcraft guidance, navigation, and control (GNC) loops, which address formation geometry maintenance, trajectory tracking, and obstacle avoidance [30]. Furthermore, a complementary method is proposed for estimating payload mass using only basic attitude measurements from onboard sensors, extending the applicability of the proposed control scheme to scenarios where payload mass is uncertain or varies over time, as in search and rescue, construction, or aerial firefighting missions [31].

The effectiveness of the proposed approach is validated through numerical simulations in a realistic test case involving a formation of two octarotors. A detailed dynamic model is employed, incorporating actuator characteristics and a blade-element representation of rotor aerodynamics. Sample delivery tasks are simulated under non-ideal conditions, including elastic cables, environmental disturbances, model uncertainties, and sensor noise.

The contributions of this work are multifold: 1) payload swing estimation is achieved without requiring dedicated hardware beyond stan-

Fig. 1. Multirotor body-fixed reference frames.

standard onboard inertial measurement units (IMUs); 2) the FGDF methodology ensures robustness against external disturbances and unmodeled dynamics [29]; 3) a procedure is introduced to estimate the three-dimensional aerodynamic disturbance force acting on each vehicle, enhancing estimation reliability in adverse wind conditions [22]; 4) payload mass estimation from simple sensor data broadens the method's applicability to variable-mass missions.

From a practical perspective, the controller is demonstrated to be compatible with widely used commercial off-the-shelf (COTS) solutions, such as the PX4 autopilot platform [32]. Furthermore, the recursive estimation algorithm can be implemented on board a single vehicle with limited inter-agent communication requirements. Thanks to the specific problem parameterization, the method remains conceptually simple while offering rich physical insights. Its general formulation makes it applicable to a variety of rotorcraft configurations, yielding improvements in flight stability, operational safety, and energy efficiency. Although the proposed estimation filter relies on a linearized representation of the coupled rotorcraft-payload system, it effectively captures the essential dynamics with satisfactory accuracy, while maintaining a notably low computational burden. This balance between model simplicity and estimation fidelity makes the method particularly well-suited for real-time onboard implementation. It is acknowledged that the filter may lose precision under extreme flight conditions involving large payload swings or highly aggressive maneuvers. However, such scenarios fall outside the scope of the present study. The intended application domain encompasses future air delivery and industrial logistics operations, where flight trajectories are required to be smooth and conservative to minimize the risk of damage to both the payload and the surrounding environment. Moreover, the proposed control strategy inherently reinforces the robustness of the estimation framework by actively limiting both the amplitude of oscillations and the magnitude of inertial accelerations, thereby ensuring that the system operates within a dynamic regime consistent with the assumptions underpinning the observer design.

2. System modeling

2.1. Reference frames

First, an Earth-fixed North-East-Down frame, $\mathcal{F}_E = \{O_E; \mathbf{x}_E, \mathbf{y}_E, \mathbf{z}_E\}$, is considered according to the definition in [5]. Provided P_i is the center of gravity of the i -th agent, two sets of right-handed orthogonal reference frames are introduced:

1. two Body-fixed frames, $\mathcal{F}_{B_i} = \{P_i; \mathbf{x}_{B_i}, \mathbf{y}_{B_i}, \mathbf{z}_{B_i}\}$, $i = 1, 2$. The longitudinal axis \mathbf{x}_{B_i} is positive out the nose of the i -th rotorcraft in

- its selected plane of symmetry, \mathbf{z}_{B_i} aims in the direction of fuselage/frame bottom, and \mathbf{y}_{B_i} completes a right-handed triad;
2. a rotorcraft structural reference frame, $\mathcal{F}_S = \{O_S; \mathbf{x}_S, \mathbf{y}_S, \mathbf{z}_S\}$, used to locate the center of gravity and all vehicle components: axes are parallel to the body-fixed frame axes, such that $\mathbf{x}_S = -\mathbf{x}_B$, $\mathbf{y}_S = \mathbf{y}_B$, and $\mathbf{z}_S = -\mathbf{z}_B$. Stationlines (ST) are measured positive aft along the longitudinal axis. Buttlines (BL) are lateral distances, positive to the right, and waterlines (WL) are measured vertically, positive upward. In what follows, without loss of generality, a sample multirotor configuration is considered. In such a case, O_S lies on the top surface of frame and is aligned vertically with drone geometric center over the $\mathbf{x}_S - \mathbf{y}_S$ plane.

A sketch of the i -th rotorcraft including the selected reference frames is reported in Fig. 1. Vector transformation between \mathcal{F}_E and \mathcal{F}_{B_i} is provided by the rotation matrix $T_{BE}(\eta_i)$ [5], where $\eta_i = [\phi_i, \theta_i, \psi_i]^T$ defines the attitude of the i -th vehicle through the classical 'roll', 'pitch', and 'yaw' angles that characterize the ZYX Tait-Bryan extrinsic rotation sequence [33]. In what follows, the subscript 'E' will be dropped for simplicity.

2.2. Equations of motion

Let $\mathbf{r}_i = [r_{x_i}, r_{y_i}, r_{z_i}]^T$ be the position of the i -th agent and $\mathbf{v}_i = [v_{x_i}, v_{y_i}, v_{z_i}]^T$ its velocity with respect to the inertial frame. A suspended load with mass m_l is connected in P_l by a cable to the i -th agent. The drones and the suspension cables are assumed to be identical. The dynamics of each agent as expressed in \mathcal{F}_E is described by:

$$\dot{\mathbf{r}}_i = \mathbf{v}_i, \quad \dot{\mathbf{v}}_i = \frac{1}{m} (m\mathbf{g} + \mathbf{f}_{l_i} + \mathbf{f}_{d_i} + \mathbf{f}_{c_i}) \quad (1)$$

where m is the mass of the rotorcraft, $\mathbf{g} = [0, 0, g]^T$ is the local gravitational acceleration vector, $\mathbf{f}_{l_i} = [f_{x_{l_i}}, f_{y_{l_i}}, f_{z_{l_i}}]^T$ is the force induced by the load on the i -th rotorcraft through the cable, and $\mathbf{f}_{d_i} = [f_{x_{d_i}}, f_{y_{d_i}}, f_{z_{d_i}}]^T$ is vehicle aerodynamic disturbance, that accounts for the contributions of rotorcraft frame drag and rotor in-plane forces. The thrust vector $\mathbf{f}_{c_i} = [f_{x_{c_i}}, f_{y_{c_i}}, f_{z_{c_i}}]^T$, directed along \mathbf{z}_{B_i} and pointing upwards, represents the only control input to Eq. (1). It is assumed that the i -th cable is connected to the center of gravity of the i -th agent, such that \mathbf{f}_{l_i} has no effect on attitude motion. Each cable is modeled as massless, under the assumption that its mass is negligible compared to the total mass of the system. It is further treated as a perfectly rigid element of constant nominal length L , implying no deformation under load and the ability to transmit both tensile and compressive forces, akin to an ideal rigid link, although, in practice, the transmission of compressive forces through cables is highly improbable.

Fig. 2. Definition of oscillation angle ζ .

With respect to payload position $\mathbf{r}_l = [r_{x_l}, r_{y_l}, r_{z_l}]^T$, an ad hoc parameterization is adopted which stems from the approach in [29]. Let P_m be the midpoint between P_1 and P_2 , with position $\mathbf{r}_m = (\mathbf{r}_1 + \mathbf{r}_2)/2$ (see Fig. 2.a). Define $\boldsymbol{\gamma} = \mathbf{r}_1 - \mathbf{r}_2$ and $\boldsymbol{\beta} = (\boldsymbol{\gamma}/\gamma) \times \mathbf{z}_E$, where $\gamma = \|\boldsymbol{\gamma}\|$ and ‘ \times ’ is the cross-product operator. Consider the reference frame $\mathcal{F}_H = \{P_m; \mathbf{x}_H, \mathbf{y}_H, \mathbf{z}_H\}$ with axes $\mathbf{x}_H = \boldsymbol{\beta}/\beta$, $\mathbf{y}_H = \boldsymbol{\gamma}/\gamma$, and $\mathbf{z}_H = \mathbf{x}_H \times \mathbf{y}_H = (\boldsymbol{\beta}/\beta) \times (\boldsymbol{\gamma}/\gamma)$, provided $\beta = \|\boldsymbol{\beta}\|$. Note that \mathbf{y}_H and \mathbf{z}_H lie on the local vertical plane Γ that contains the vehicles, while \mathbf{x}_H identifies the direction orthogonal to Γ , as shown in Fig. 2.b. Vector transformation between \mathcal{F}_H and \mathcal{F}_E is provided by the rotation matrix $\mathbf{T}_{EH} = [\mathbf{x}_H \ \mathbf{y}_H \ \mathbf{z}_H]$, where unit vector components are expressed in \mathcal{F}_E as

$$\mathbf{x}_H = [r_{y_1} - r_{y_2}, r_{x_2} - r_{x_1}, 0]^T / \beta \quad (2)$$

$$\mathbf{y}_H = [r_{x_1} - r_{x_2}, r_{y_1} - r_{y_2}, r_{z_1} - r_{z_2}]^T / \gamma \quad (3)$$

$$\mathbf{z}_H = \left[-(r_{x_1} - r_{x_2})(r_{z_1} - r_{z_2}), -(r_{y_1} - r_{y_2})(r_{z_1} - r_{z_2}), (r_{x_1} - r_{x_2})^2 + (r_{y_1} - r_{y_2})^2 \right]^T / (\beta\gamma) \quad (4)$$

with

$$\beta = \sqrt{(r_{x_1} - r_{x_2})^2 + (r_{y_1} - r_{y_2})^2} \quad (5)$$

$$\gamma = \sqrt{(r_{x_1} - r_{x_2})^2 + (r_{y_1} - r_{y_2})^2 + (r_{z_1} - r_{z_2})^2} \quad (6)$$

Let $\hat{\mathbf{l}} = \mathbf{l}/\|\mathbf{l}\|$ be the unit vector directed from P_m to P_1 , where $\mathbf{l} = \mathbf{r}_1 - \mathbf{r}_m$ and $\|\mathbf{l}\| = \sqrt{L^2 - \gamma^2/4}$. Payload position is parameterized through the angle $-\pi \leq \zeta \leq \pi$, $\zeta \neq \pm\pi/2$, obtained from load rotation about \mathbf{y}_H . Given $\hat{\mathbf{l}} = \mathbf{T}_{EH} \hat{\mathbf{l}}_H$, it is $\hat{\mathbf{l}}_H = [\sin \zeta, 0, \cos \zeta]^T$ and payload position is calculated as a function of ζ , \mathbf{r}_1 , and \mathbf{r}_2 . It follows:

$$\mathbf{r}_l = \mathbf{r}_m + \|\mathbf{l}\| \mathbf{T}_{EH} [\sin \zeta, 0, \cos \zeta]^T \quad (7)$$

$$= (\mathbf{r}_1 + \mathbf{r}_2)/2 + (\sqrt{L^2 - \gamma^2/4}) \mathbf{T}_{EH} [\sin \zeta, 0, \cos \zeta]^T$$

Let $\boldsymbol{\lambda} = [\mathbf{r}_1^T \ \mathbf{r}_2^T \ \zeta]^T \in \mathbb{R}^7$ be a vector of generalized coordinates. The Lagrangian equation with respect to $\boldsymbol{\lambda}$ is [29]:

$$\frac{d}{dt} \left(\frac{\partial E}{\partial \dot{\boldsymbol{\lambda}}} \right) - \frac{\partial E}{\partial \boldsymbol{\lambda}} = \boldsymbol{\tau} \quad (8)$$

where $E = K - U$ is Lagrangian function and $\boldsymbol{\tau} \in \mathbb{R}^7$ is a vector of generalized forces. K is system kinetic energy, given by

$$K = \frac{1}{2} m (\dot{\mathbf{r}}_1^T \dot{\mathbf{r}}_1 + \dot{\mathbf{r}}_2^T \dot{\mathbf{r}}_2) + \frac{1}{2} m_l \dot{\mathbf{r}}_l^T \dot{\mathbf{r}}_l \quad (9)$$

where $\dot{\mathbf{r}}_l$ denotes load velocity as obtained from Eq. (7), namely:

$$\begin{aligned} \dot{\mathbf{r}}_l = & (\dot{\mathbf{r}}_1 + \dot{\mathbf{r}}_2)/2 - \frac{\gamma \dot{\gamma}}{2\sqrt{4L^2 - \gamma^2}} \mathbf{T}_{EH} [\sin \zeta, 0, \cos \zeta]^T \\ & + (\sqrt{L^2 - \gamma^2/4}) \{ \dot{\mathbf{T}}_{EH} [\sin \zeta, 0, \cos \zeta]^T \\ & + \mathbf{T}_{EH} [\cos \zeta, 0, -\sin \zeta]^T \dot{\zeta} \} \end{aligned} \quad (10)$$

With respect to time-derivatives $\dot{\mathbf{T}}_{EH}$ and $\dot{\gamma}$ in Eq. (10), it is $\dot{\mathbf{T}}_{EH} = [\dot{\mathbf{x}}_H \ \dot{\mathbf{y}}_H \ \dot{\mathbf{z}}_H]$, where $\dot{\mathbf{x}}_H = (\dot{\boldsymbol{\beta}}\boldsymbol{\beta} - \boldsymbol{\beta}\dot{\boldsymbol{\beta}})/\beta^2$, $\dot{\mathbf{y}}_H = (\dot{\boldsymbol{\gamma}}\boldsymbol{\gamma} - \boldsymbol{\gamma}\dot{\boldsymbol{\gamma}})/\gamma^2$, and $\dot{\mathbf{z}}_H = [(\dot{\boldsymbol{\beta}}\boldsymbol{\beta} - \boldsymbol{\beta}\dot{\boldsymbol{\beta}})/\beta^2] \times (\boldsymbol{\gamma}/\gamma) + [(\dot{\boldsymbol{\gamma}}\boldsymbol{\gamma} - \boldsymbol{\gamma}\dot{\boldsymbol{\gamma}})/\gamma^2] \times (\boldsymbol{\beta}/\beta)$ while

$$\dot{\boldsymbol{\beta}} = [\dot{r}_{y_1} - \dot{r}_{y_2}, \dot{r}_{x_2} - \dot{r}_{x_1}, 0]^T \quad (11)$$

$$\dot{\boldsymbol{\beta}} = [(\dot{r}_{x_1} - \dot{r}_{x_2})(r_{x_1} - r_{x_2}) + (\dot{r}_{y_1} - \dot{r}_{y_2})(r_{y_1} - r_{y_2})] / \beta \quad (12)$$

$$\dot{\boldsymbol{\gamma}} = [\dot{r}_{x_1} - \dot{r}_{x_2}, \dot{r}_{y_1} - \dot{r}_{y_2}, \dot{r}_{z_1} - \dot{r}_{z_2}]^T \quad (13)$$

$$\begin{aligned} \dot{\boldsymbol{\gamma}} = & [(\dot{r}_{x_1} - \dot{r}_{x_2})(r_{x_1} - r_{x_2}) + (\dot{r}_{y_1} - \dot{r}_{y_2})(r_{y_1} - r_{y_2}) \\ & + (\dot{r}_{z_1} - \dot{r}_{z_2})(r_{z_1} - r_{z_2})] / \gamma \end{aligned} \quad (14)$$

Potential energy U is related to the vertical displacement of the agents and the suspended load:

$$U = -mg(r_{z_1} + r_{z_2}) - m_l g r_{z_l} \quad (15)$$

Given the energy contributions in Eqs. (9) and (15) and taking into account the state of the load as described by Eqs. (7) and (10), the Lagrangian equation is manipulated into the system:

$$\dot{\boldsymbol{\lambda}} = \boldsymbol{\mu}, \quad \mathbf{M}(\boldsymbol{\lambda}) \dot{\boldsymbol{\mu}} + \mathbf{C}(\boldsymbol{\lambda}, \boldsymbol{\mu}) \boldsymbol{\mu} + \mathbf{G}(\boldsymbol{\lambda}) = \boldsymbol{\tau} \quad (16)$$

where $\boldsymbol{\mu} = [\mathbf{v}_1^T \ \mathbf{v}_2^T \ \dot{\zeta}]^T \in \mathbb{R}^7$. For the sake of brevity, the highly-nonlinear and lengthy expressions of terms $\mathbf{M}(\boldsymbol{\lambda})$, $\mathbf{C}(\boldsymbol{\lambda}, \boldsymbol{\mu})$, and $\mathbf{G}(\boldsymbol{\lambda})$ are not detailed in the present framework but can be made available to the reader upon request. The generalized force vector $\boldsymbol{\tau} = \boldsymbol{\tau}_c + \boldsymbol{\tau}_d \in \mathbb{R}^7$ is made of a control contribution, $\boldsymbol{\tau}_c = [\mathbf{f}_c^T \ \mathbf{f}_c^T \ 0]^T$, and a disturbance term, $\boldsymbol{\tau}_d = [\mathbf{f}_d^T \ \mathbf{f}_d^T \ 0]^T$, that mostly accounts for the aerodynamic drag of the multirotor.

3. Swing state estimation

3.1. System linearization

Let $\bar{\boldsymbol{\gamma}} = [\bar{\gamma}_x, \bar{\gamma}_y, 0]^T$ be the prescribed mutual distance vector between the two agents of the formation, with components expressed in \mathcal{F}_E , selected such that $\bar{\boldsymbol{\gamma}} = \sqrt{\bar{\gamma}_x^2 + \bar{\gamma}_y^2} < 2L$. The system in Eq. (16) is linearized about the equilibrium $(\bar{\boldsymbol{y}}, \bar{\boldsymbol{u}})$, where $\bar{\boldsymbol{y}} = [\bar{\boldsymbol{\lambda}}^T \ \bar{\boldsymbol{\mu}}^T]^T = [\mathbf{r}_1^T (r_1 - \bar{\boldsymbol{\gamma}})^T \ \mathbf{0}_{1 \times 8}]^T \in \mathbb{R}^{14}$ is representative of a hovering flight where the three point-masses lie on the local vertical plane Γ (see Fig. 2), provided the aerodynamic disturbances are a constant, $\bar{\mathbf{f}}_{d_1}$ and $\bar{\mathbf{f}}_{d_2}$. The term $\bar{\boldsymbol{u}} = [\bar{\mathbf{u}}_1^T \ \bar{\mathbf{u}}_2^T]^T \in \mathbb{R}^6$ represents the proper equilibrium force, where $\bar{\mathbf{u}}_1 = \bar{\mathbf{f}}_{c_1} + \bar{\mathbf{f}}_{d_1}$ and $\bar{\mathbf{u}}_2 = \bar{\mathbf{f}}_{c_2} + \bar{\mathbf{f}}_{d_2}$. In such a case $\dot{\zeta} = 0$, $\dot{\boldsymbol{\gamma}} = 0$, and Agent 2 is required to maintain the prescribed position $\bar{\mathbf{r}}_2 = \mathbf{r}_1 - \bar{\boldsymbol{\gamma}}$. The generalized equilibrium force is obtained as $\bar{\boldsymbol{\tau}} = \bar{\boldsymbol{\tau}}_c + \bar{\boldsymbol{\tau}}_d = \mathbf{G}(\bar{\boldsymbol{\lambda}})$. Let $M = 2m + m_l$ be the total system mass and define $\xi_i = 2(1 - i) + 1$. Taking into account the first 6 components in $\bar{\boldsymbol{\tau}}$, the proper equilibrium force $\bar{\mathbf{u}}_i$ is obtained as

$$\bar{\mathbf{u}}_i = \left[\frac{g m_l \xi_i \bar{\gamma}_x}{2\sqrt{4L^2 - \bar{\gamma}^2}}, \frac{g m_l \xi_i \bar{\gamma}_y}{2\sqrt{4L^2 - \bar{\gamma}^2}}, -\frac{g M}{2} \right]^T \quad (17)$$

while the control force generated by the i -th agent is

$$\bar{\mathbf{f}}_{c_i} = [\bar{f}_{x_{c_i}}, \bar{f}_{y_{c_i}}, \bar{f}_{z_{c_i}}]^T = \bar{\mathbf{u}}_i - \bar{\mathbf{f}}_{d_i} \quad (18)$$

Theorem 1. Consider the slung-load system described by Eq. (16). The equilibrium point $(\bar{\mathbf{y}}, \bar{\mathbf{u}})$, characterized by Eq. (17) and obtained by the control force in Eq. (18), satisfies the second-order equation:

$$a_i m_l^2 + b_i m_l + c_i = 0 \quad (19)$$

where

$$a_i = \frac{g^2}{4} \left(\frac{\bar{\gamma}^2}{4L^2 - \bar{\gamma}^2} - \tan^2 \bar{\alpha}_i \right) \quad (20)$$

$$b_i = -g \left[\xi_i \frac{\bar{f}_{x_{d_i}} \bar{\gamma}_x + \bar{f}_{y_{d_i}} \bar{\gamma}_y}{\sqrt{4L^2 - \bar{\gamma}^2}} + (\bar{f}_{z_{d_i}} + m g) \tan^2 \bar{\alpha}_i \right] \quad (21)$$

$$c_i = \bar{f}_{x_{d_i}}^2 + \bar{f}_{y_{d_i}}^2 - (\bar{f}_{z_{d_i}} + m g)^2 \tan^2 \bar{\alpha}_i \quad (22)$$

for $i = 1, 2$, provided $\bar{\alpha}_i > 0$ is the angle between $-\mathbf{z}_E$ and the i -th equilibrium control force $\bar{\mathbf{f}}_{c_i}$. In the case when the agents of the formation are multirotors, it follows $\bar{\alpha}_i = \arccos(\cos \bar{\phi}_i \cos \bar{\theta}_i)$, provided $\bar{\boldsymbol{\eta}}_i = [\bar{\phi}_i, \bar{\theta}_i, \bar{\psi}_i]^T$ is the equilibrium attitude of the i -th agent.

Proof. See Appendix A. \square

Remark 1. Assume the disturbance force components $\bar{f}_{x_{d_i}}$, $\bar{f}_{y_{d_i}}$, and $\bar{f}_{z_{d_i}}$ can be estimated and the attitude variables $\bar{\phi}_i$ and $\bar{\theta}_i$ are measured in a hovering condition. Eq. (19) can be solved to estimate m_l in all those cases where payload mass is uncertain or not known a-priori. In this respect, an initial hovering maneuver can be planned where the formation is stabilized in the desired equilibrium condition and the estimated payload mass \bar{m}_l is computed as a steady-state solution to Eq. (19). For values of practical application, two real-distinct solutions are obtained, between which the negative one is excluded. The analysis can be performed for either vehicle, nominally leading to the same solution even though different disturbances and attitude variables characterize the multirotors. As an alternative, without loss of generality, Agent 1 can be assumed as the formation leader where all necessary information converge to allow all estimation procedures. With respect to the estimation of disturbance forces, different methods are available in the literature, where disturbance observers (DOBs) are typically designed to support the control action in rejecting both external disturbances and effects of model uncertainties [34].

Remark 2. To prevent singularities in the proposed mathematical formulation, a constraint is imposed on the design of the prescribed mutual distance vector between the two agents, namely $\bar{\gamma} = \sqrt{\bar{\gamma}_x^2 + \bar{\gamma}_y^2} < 2L$. Assuming Agent 1 is stabilized at \mathbf{r}_1 and Agent 2 lies at $\mathbf{r}_1 - \bar{\boldsymbol{\gamma}}$, the determinant of $\mathbf{M}(\lambda)$ becomes:

$$\det(\mathbf{M}) = \frac{m_l m^4}{\bar{\gamma}^2} \left[m_l (2m_l + m) L^4 + m^2 \bar{\gamma}^2 \left(L^2 - \frac{\bar{\gamma}^2}{4} \right) \right] \quad (23)$$

Given m , m_l , and L , the configuration becomes ill-posed when $\det(\mathbf{M}) = 0$, which situation occurs for values of $\bar{\gamma}$ that satisfy the equation:

$$m^2 \bar{\gamma}^4 - 4m^2 L^2 \bar{\gamma}^2 - 4m_l (2m_l + m) L^4 = 0 \quad (24)$$

that does not depend on the particular swing state of the payload. The 4-th order polynomial in Eq. (24) has only one real positive root, given by $\bar{\gamma}^* = 2L \sqrt{1 + m_l/(2m)}$. Since $\bar{\gamma}^* > 2L$, the suggested constraint allows for a well-posed and safe configuration of the formation.

Let $\mathbf{y} = [\lambda^T \boldsymbol{\mu}^T]^T \in \mathbb{R}^{14}$ and $\mathbf{u} = [\mathbf{u}_1^T \mathbf{u}_2^T]^T \in \mathbb{R}^6$ be the state and input vectors respectively describing the dynamics in Eq. (16), linearized about the considered equilibrium condition. The standard state-space representation $\dot{\mathbf{y}} = \mathbf{A} \mathbf{y} + \mathbf{B} \mathbf{u}$ is derived where $\mathbf{A} \in \mathbb{R}^{14 \times 14}$ is the state matrix,

$$\mathbf{A} = \left[\begin{array}{c|c} \mathbf{0}_{7 \times 7} & \mathbf{I}_7 \\ \hline A_{8,1} & A_{8,2} & \dots & A_{8,7} \\ A_{9,1} & A_{9,2} & \dots & A_{9,7} \\ \vdots & \vdots & \ddots & \vdots \\ A_{14,1} & A_{14,2} & \dots & A_{14,7} \end{array} \right] \mathbf{0}_{7 \times 7}, \quad (25)$$

and $\mathbf{B} \in \mathbb{R}^{14 \times 6}$ is the input matrix,

$$\mathbf{B} = \left[\begin{array}{c|c} \mathbf{0}_{7 \times 6} & \\ \hline B_{8,1} & B_{8,2} & \dots & B_{8,6} \\ B_{9,1} & B_{9,2} & \dots & B_{9,6} \\ \vdots & \vdots & \ddots & \vdots \\ B_{14,1} & B_{14,2} & \dots & B_{14,6} \end{array} \right] \quad (26)$$

In the present framework, \mathbf{I}_p is the unit matrix with dimension p , while $\mathbf{0}_{q \times r}$ is the null matrix with dimension $q \times r$. The components of matrices in Eqs. (25) and (26) are detailed in Appendix B.

3.2. Filter recursive equations

Let $\mathbf{x} = [\zeta, \dot{\zeta}]^T \in \mathbb{R}^2$ be the state vector representing payload oscillation dynamics only. The linear time-invariant state-space model $\dot{\mathbf{x}} = \mathbf{A}_\zeta \mathbf{x} + \mathbf{B}_\zeta \mathbf{u}$ is extracted from Eqs. (25) and (26), where

$$\mathbf{A}_\zeta = \begin{bmatrix} 0 & 1 \\ A_{14,7} & 0 \end{bmatrix}, \quad (27)$$

and

$$\mathbf{B}_\zeta = \begin{bmatrix} 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 \\ B_{14,1} & B_{14,2} & B_{14,3} & B_{14,4} & B_{14,5} & B_{14,6} \end{bmatrix} \quad (28)$$

The considered dynamic model is reformulated into difference equations where the true state vector $\mathbf{x}^{(k)}$ at time k propagates according to $\mathbf{x}^{(k+1)} = \boldsymbol{\Phi}^{(k)} \mathbf{x}^{(k)} + \boldsymbol{\Psi}^{(k)} \mathbf{u}^{(k)}$. The state transition matrix for the estimation algorithm is obtained as $\boldsymbol{\Phi}^{(k)} = \boldsymbol{\Phi} = \exp(\mathbf{A}_\zeta \Delta t)$, where $\Delta t = t_{k+1} - t_k$ is the sampling interval. The control-input model is calculated as $\boldsymbol{\Psi}^{(k)} = \boldsymbol{\Psi} = \mathbf{A}_\zeta^{-1} (\boldsymbol{\Phi} - \mathbf{I}_2) \mathbf{B}_\zeta$.

The linearization of system dynamics in Eq. (16) provides additional information related to vehicles acceleration on the local horizontal plane. As an example, the following equation is obtained for Agent 1:

$$\mathbf{a}_1 = \boldsymbol{\alpha}_1 [\mathbf{r}_1^T \mathbf{r}_2^T]^T + \boldsymbol{\beta}_1 \mathbf{u} + \lambda_1 \boldsymbol{\zeta} \quad (29)$$

where $\mathbf{a}_1 = [a_{x_1}, a_{y_1}, a_{z_1}]^T = [\dot{v}_{x_1}, \dot{v}_{y_1}, \dot{v}_{z_1}]^T$ is the acceleration of Agent 1 as expressed in \mathcal{F}_E , provided

$$\boldsymbol{\alpha}_1 = \begin{bmatrix} A_{8,1} & A_{8,2} & A_{8,3} & A_{8,4} & A_{8,5} & A_{8,6} \\ A_{9,1} & A_{9,2} & A_{9,3} & A_{9,4} & A_{9,5} & A_{9,6} \\ A_{10,1} & A_{10,2} & A_{10,3} & A_{10,4} & A_{10,5} & A_{10,6} \end{bmatrix}, \quad (30)$$

$$\boldsymbol{\beta}_1 = \begin{bmatrix} B_{8,1} & B_{8,2} & B_{8,3} & B_{8,4} & B_{8,5} & B_{8,6} \\ B_{9,1} & B_{9,2} & B_{9,3} & B_{9,4} & B_{9,5} & B_{9,6} \\ B_{10,1} & B_{10,2} & B_{10,3} & B_{10,4} & B_{10,5} & B_{10,6} \end{bmatrix}, \quad (31)$$

and $\lambda_1 = [A_{8,7}, A_{9,7}, 0]^T$ are matrix subsets of \mathbf{A} and \mathbf{B} , with $\boldsymbol{\alpha}_1, \boldsymbol{\beta}_1 \in \mathbb{R}^{3 \times 6}$, and $\lambda_1 \in \mathbb{R}^{3 \times 1}$. It is noted from Eqs. (2)–(4) that the ad hoc reference frame \mathcal{F}_H in the equilibrium condition is defined by unit vectors $\bar{\mathbf{x}}_H = [\bar{\gamma}_y, -\bar{\gamma}_x, 0]^T / \bar{\gamma}$, $\bar{\mathbf{y}}_H = [\bar{\gamma}_x, \bar{\gamma}_y, 0]^T / \bar{\gamma}$, and $\bar{\mathbf{z}}_H = [0, 0, 1]^T$. By applying the transformation $\bar{\mathbf{T}}_{HE} = \bar{\mathbf{T}}_{EH}^T = [\bar{\mathbf{x}}_H \ \bar{\mathbf{y}}_H \ \bar{\mathbf{z}}_H]^T$ to both sides of Eq. (29), one obtains

$$\bar{\mathbf{T}}_{HE} \left(\mathbf{a}_1 - \boldsymbol{\alpha}_1 [\mathbf{r}_1^T \mathbf{r}_2^T]^T - \boldsymbol{\beta}_1 \mathbf{u} \right) = \left[\frac{g m_l}{2m} \boldsymbol{\zeta}, 0, 0 \right]^T \quad (32)$$

where the definition of λ_1 is accounted with the values of $A_{8,7}$ and $A_{9,7}$ in Appendix B. Assume that, at time k the input $\mathbf{u}^{(k)}$ is known while acceleration $\mathbf{a}_1^{(k)}$ and position information $\mathbf{r}_1^{(k)}$ and $\mathbf{r}_2^{(k)}$ are made available from sensors. Equation (32) infers the observability of oscillation angle ζ from acceleration and control contributions along \mathbf{x}_H only. Hence,

by focusing on the first component, one obtains the measurement ζ_m of swing angle, namely

$$\zeta_m^{(k)} = \frac{2m}{g m_l} \bar{x}_H^T \left(\mathbf{a}_1^{(k)} - \alpha_1 \left[\mathbf{r}_1^{(k)T} \mathbf{r}_2^{(k)T} \right]^T - \beta_1 \mathbf{u}^{(k)} \right) \quad (33)$$

The observation $z^{(k)} = \zeta_m^{(k)}$ tracks the considered dynamic process as in $z^{(k)} = \mathbf{H} \mathbf{x}^{(k)}$, where $\mathbf{H} = [1 \ 0]$ is the time-invariant observation matrix. Measurements are assumed to be corrupted by noise $v^{(k)}$ with variance R , that is $z^{(k)} = \mathbf{H} \mathbf{x}^{(k)} + v^{(k)}$. The estimation problem is solved by a set of Kalman-like recursive equations where the gain matrix is computed through the formal minimization of a cost function, with no other assumption [28]. The approach follows that proposed in [29], where the FGDF is described in detail. The same nomenclature is here adopted.

Remark 3. Input $\mathbf{u}^{(k)}$ in Eq. (33) is assumed to be known, accounting for both disturbance and control forces. With respect to the knowledge of control force, an approximate solution is provided for a multirotor platform, based on the approach in [22]. Starting from the definition in Sec. 2.2, the i -th vehicle control force is expressed as $\mathbf{f}_{ci} = -T_i \mathbf{z}_{B_i} = \mathbf{T}_{BE}^T(\eta_i)[0, 0, -T_i]^T$, where T_i is net thrust generated along \mathbf{z}_{B_i} . Taking into account Eq. (1) and including the estimated external disturbance $\tilde{\mathbf{f}}_{d_i}$, the reconstructed thrust magnitude \tilde{T}_i is calculated as

$$\tilde{T}_i = \left\| m \mathbf{a}_i - m \tilde{\mathbf{g}} - \tilde{\mathbf{f}}_{l_i} - \tilde{\mathbf{f}}_{d_i} \right\| \quad (34)$$

where $\tilde{\mathbf{g}}$ is measured gravity acceleration and $\tilde{\mathbf{f}}_{l_i}$ is the estimated force induced by the load on the i -th multirotor. Under the simplifying assumption that maneuvers are performed near the equilibrium $(\bar{\mathbf{y}}, \bar{\mathbf{u}})$, it is possible to assign $m \tilde{\mathbf{g}} + \tilde{\mathbf{f}}_{l_i} \approx -\bar{\mathbf{u}}_i$, where $\bar{\mathbf{u}}_i$ is retrieved from Eq. (17). Reconstructed control force for filtering purposes is thus $\bar{\mathbf{u}}_i = \mathbf{T}_{BE}^T(\tilde{\eta}_i)[0, 0, -\tilde{T}_i]^T$, provided $\tilde{\eta}_i$ is obtained from measured attitude and $\tilde{T}_i = \left\| m \mathbf{a}_i + \bar{\mathbf{u}}_i - \tilde{\mathbf{f}}_{d_i} \right\|$. Extension of the proposed method to conventional helicopter configurations can be conceived with minimum effort by accounting for both tail rotor and main rotor contributions in the estimation of net control force.

Fig. 3 suggests a suitable architecture for the implementation of FGDF in a real application scenario. Without loss of generality, Agent 1 is assumed to be the leader, where both payload mass and swing state estimation routines are computed. On condition that each vehicle is equipped with a DOB, the amount of transmission data is reduced to a minimum, that includes position \mathbf{r}_2 and reconstructed input force \mathbf{u}_2 (from Agent 2 to Agent 1) and estimated swing state $\tilde{\mathbf{x}}$ (from Agent 1 to Agent 2), the latter being available to generate a common payload control action. With respect to the disturbance observation and the control force estimation respectively discussed in Remarks 1 and 3, an alternative method of practical application will be proposed in Sec. 4, based on the particular control strategy of PX4 standard [32].

4. Results

4.1. Simulation platform

Simulations are performed in Matlab[®] environment with a 4th-order Runge–Kutta solver frequency of 500 Hz [35]. The agents of the formation are two identical octarotors modeled as rigid bodies. The modeling follows the same approach and nomenclature adopted in [10], where the selected platform, characterized by a planar set of contra-rotating propellers, is described in detail. For the sake of brevity, only relevant system parameters are listed in Table 1. The payload is assumed to be a point mass attached through a hook point H , distinct from rotorcraft center of gravity. The payload is affected by aerodynamic drag, provided $A_l = \pi R_l^2$ is the frontal area of an equivalent sphere with radius $R_l = 0.5$ m and drag coefficient $C_{d_l} = 0.5$:

Fig. 3. Suitable architecture for FGDF implementation.

Table 1
Relevant system parameters.

Parameter	Symbol	Value	Units
Multirotor			
Mass	m	70	kg
Center of gravity position	$ST A_{CP} = B L_P$	0	m
	$W L_P$	-0.15	m
Moments of inertia	J_{11}	10.61	kg m ²
	J_{22}	10.31	kg m ²
	J_{33}	19.74	kg m ²
	J_{12}	0.037	kg m ²
	J_{13}	-0.043	kg m ²
	J_{23}	-0.003	kg m ²
Center of pressure position	$ST A_{CP} = B L_{CP}$	0	m
	$W L_{CP}$	-0.125	m
Frame drag areas	$A_1 = A_2$	0.22	m ²
	A_3	1.03	m ²
Propeller			
Number of blades	n_b	2	
Radius	R	0.5	m
Mean aerodynamic chord	\bar{c}	0.086	m
Chord @ 75% R	c_{75}	0.103	m
Lift curve slope	a	5.9	rad ⁻¹
Pre-cone angle	a_0	0	rad
Root pitch angle	θ_0	0.7854	rad
Total twist	θ_l	-0.6981	rad
Load			
Mass	m_l	100	kg
Reference area	A_l	0.785	m ²
Drag coefficient (sphere)	C_{d_l}	0.5	
Cable			
Nominal length	L	15	m
Hooke's constant	K	90 950	N m ⁻¹
Damping coefficient	C	215	N m ⁻¹ s
Hook point position	$ST A_H = B L_H$	0	m
	$W L_H$	-0.2	m

Fig. 4. The i -th multirotor control scheme based on PX4 autopilot architecture [32].

$$f_{d_i} = -\frac{1}{2} \rho A_l C_{d_l} \|\mathbf{v}_i\| \mathbf{v}_i \quad (35)$$

Air parameters are calculated by the International Standard Atmosphere (ISA) model as a function of altitude [36]. Local gravitational data are provided by the World Geodetic System 1984 model as a function of vehicle latitude, longitude, and altitude [37]. Let $\mathbf{c}_i = \mathbf{r}_l - \mathbf{r}_i$ be the vector describing the orientation and length of the i -th cable. The force \mathbf{f}_{l_i} in Eq. (1) is calculated by the equation

$$\mathbf{f}_{l_i} = (K \Delta L_i + C \Delta \dot{L}_i) \hat{\mathbf{c}}_i \quad (36)$$

where K is the elastic constant, $\Delta L_i = \|\mathbf{c}_i\| - L$ and $\Delta \dot{L}_i$ are, respectively, the elastic deformation and its time derivative, and $\hat{\mathbf{c}}_i = \mathbf{c}_i / \|\mathbf{c}_i\|$ is a unit vector. With respect to the classical Hookes' model in [10], cable internal damping is accounted by coefficient C . The dynamics of each electric propulsion unit, comprising an Electronic Speed Controller (ESC) and a brushless motor, are represented by a first-order transfer function with time constant $\tau_{em} = 0.06$ s, capturing both electrical and mechanical non-idealities. This transfer function maps the commanded rotor angular rate to the actual rate delivered by the motor shaft.

4.2. Control system design

A controller is designed and empirically validated to fulfill 1) formation-keeping and trajectory-tracking, 2) inter-agent collision avoidance, and 3) active payload stabilization. Control tasks are performed, without loss of generality, through a cascaded algorithm based on PX4 architecture and notation [32]. Such control solution is known to stabilize the i -th octarotor according to different flight modes that include the tracking of an Earth-fixed set-point position \mathbf{r}_{sp_i} , velocity \mathbf{v}_{sp_i} , or acceleration \mathbf{a}_{sp_i} (see Fig. 4, where $\mathbf{a}_{sp_i}^{(VC)}$ is the acceleration set-point generated by the available Velocity Controller). With respect to formation control, assume the i -th vehicle is required to keep a prescribed distance from a reference point P_r , identified by vector position $\mathbf{r}_r(t)$ and moving with velocity $\mathbf{v}_r = \dot{\mathbf{r}}_r$. Provided D_i is the i -th agent required position, given by $\bar{\mathbf{r}}_i$, it is $\mathbf{r}_r + \mathbf{d}_i = \mathbf{r}_i$ and $\mathbf{r}_r + \bar{\mathbf{d}}_i = \bar{\mathbf{r}}_i$, where $\mathbf{d}_i = [d_{x_i}, d_{y_i}, d_{z_i}]^T$ and $\bar{\mathbf{d}}_i = [\bar{d}_{x_i}, \bar{d}_{y_i}, \bar{d}_{z_i}]^T$ respectively indicate the current and the required relative distance between the i -th agent and the reference point (see Fig. 5). It is assumed that, when the i -th agent reaches the desired position D_i , formation midpoint P_m exactly tracks P_r . Based on the definition of $\bar{\mathbf{y}}$ in Sec. 3.1, it follows $\bar{\mathbf{d}}_1 = -\bar{\mathbf{d}}_2 = [\bar{y}_x/2, \bar{y}_y/2, 0]^T$ and the set-point position in Fig. 4 becomes $\mathbf{r}_{sp_i} = \bar{\mathbf{r}}_i = \mathbf{r}_r + \bar{\mathbf{d}}_i$.

Desired acceleration $\mathbf{a}_{sp_i} = [a_{sp_{x_i}}, a_{sp_{y_i}}, a_{sp_{z_i}}]^T$ for the i -th multirotor is designed as

$$\mathbf{a}_{sp_i} = \mathbf{a}_{sp_i}^{(VC)} + \mathbf{a}_{sp_i}^{(CAC)} + \mathbf{a}_{sp_i}^{(PC)} \quad (37)$$

Fig. 5. Definition of current (P_i) and desired (D_i) position of the i -th agent.

where $\mathbf{a}_{sp_i}^{(VC)}$ accounts for formation stabilization, $\mathbf{a}_{sp_i}^{(CAC)}$ provides Collision Avoidance Control capabilities, and $\mathbf{a}_{sp_i}^{(PC)}$ implements Payload Control strategies.

With respect to $\mathbf{a}_{sp_i}^{(CAC)}$, the method proposed in [30] is adopted, based on the definition of potential function

$$V_p(\boldsymbol{\gamma}) = \frac{1}{4} \left[\frac{(\bar{\mathbf{y}} - \boldsymbol{\gamma})^T (\bar{\mathbf{y}} - \boldsymbol{\gamma})}{\boldsymbol{\gamma}^T \boldsymbol{\gamma} - R_{sph}^2} \right]^2 \quad (38)$$

where $R_{sph} < \bar{y}/2$ is the radius of a sphere, centered at P_i , representing a safety zone for the i -th agent. The acceleration contribution allowing for inter-agent collision avoidance is thus:

$$\mathbf{a}_{sp_i}^{(CAC)} = \xi_i K_a \nabla V_p|_{\boldsymbol{\gamma}} \quad (39)$$

where $K_a > 0$ is a control gain and

$$\nabla V_p|_{\boldsymbol{\gamma}} = -\frac{(\bar{\mathbf{y}} - \boldsymbol{\gamma}) \|\bar{\mathbf{y}} - \boldsymbol{\gamma}\|^2}{(\boldsymbol{\gamma}^T \boldsymbol{\gamma} - R_{sph}^2)^2} - \frac{\boldsymbol{\gamma} \|\bar{\mathbf{y}} - \boldsymbol{\gamma}\|^4}{(\boldsymbol{\gamma}^T \boldsymbol{\gamma} - R_{sph}^2)^3} \quad (40)$$

is the gradient of potential function in Eq. (38) with respect to $\boldsymbol{\gamma}$. In the present case, it is $R_{sph} = 2$ m and $K_a = 0.05$ m²/s².

The proposed payload controller is structured as

$$\mathbf{a}_{sp_i}^{(PC)} = (k_p \zeta + k_d \dot{\zeta}) \mathbf{x}_H, \quad (41)$$

being directed over the local horizontal plane in the direction of \mathbf{x}_H , where k_p and k_d are positive gains and ζ and $\dot{\zeta}$ are estimated through the FGDF. In the present framework, it is $k_p = 9$ m/(rad s²) and $k_d = 2$ m/(rad s).

4.3. Measurement setup

Non-ideal sensing behavior is considered where noise, bias, and sensor positioning errors are introduced and described from a numerical standpoint. Onboard computer is located in $STAP_{IX} = BL_{PIX} = 0$ m and $WL_{PIX} = -0.1$ m, with axes aligned with \mathcal{F}_B -axes. To simulate the effects of sensor noise, zero-mean Gaussian white noise is added to each Euler angle and angular velocity measurement, with standard deviations $\sigma_\alpha = 0.018$ deg and $\sigma_\omega = 0.095$ deg/s, respectively. The body-fixed accelerometer readings are obtained by adding white Gaussian noise with $\sigma_{acc} = 0.015$ m/s² and constant bias $\mathbf{b}_{acc_1} = [0.015, -0.01, 0.002]^T$ m/s² and $\mathbf{b}_{acc_2} = [-0.004, 0.007, -0.02]^T$ m/s² to the simulated values of Vehicle 1 and 2, respectively. Error is also considered for vehicle position and velocity expressed in \mathcal{F}_E , provided standard deviations $\sigma_p|_{xy} = 0.074$ m and $\sigma_v|_{xy} = 0.009$ m/s affect the motion over the local-horizontal plane, while $\sigma_p|_z = 0.034$ m and $\sigma_v|_z = 0.005$ m/s characterize the vertical channel. The onboard computer operates at a frequency of 100 Hz (sample time $\Delta t = 0.01$ s) and a fixed time delay,

Fig. 6. Case 1: (a) stabilization of formation error, (b) static estimation of payload mass.

$t_d = 0.04$ s, is accounted for local processing and communication issues between the agents of the formation. Note that, among all broadcast signals, the reference trajectory information (provided, for example, by a ground control station) must be included. Same consideration holds for the mutual transmission of agent position data to reconstruct the $\mathbf{x}_H = \mathbf{x}_H(\mathbf{r}_1, \mathbf{r}_2)$ -term in Eq. (41).

Based on the particular control strategy of PX4 standard in Fig. 4, a simple yet effective method is adopted to retrieve the input force value, $\mathbf{u}_i = \mathbf{f}_{c_i} + \mathbf{f}_{d_i}$. Assuming ideal electric motors, the thrust value is computed as $\tilde{T}_i = m \|\mathbf{a}_{sp_i}\|$. By accounting for attitude dynamics, the generated control force as expressed in \mathcal{F}_E is finally estimated as $\tilde{\mathbf{f}}_{c_i} = \mathbf{T}_{BE}^T(\tilde{\boldsymbol{\eta}}_i)[0, 0, -\tilde{T}_i]^T$. With respect to the analysis of external disturbances, it is noted that velocity controller in Fig. 4 is based on a simple PID implementation [32], where the error between the set-point and the measured velocity is transformed into the desired acceleration $\mathbf{a}_{sp_i}^{(VC)} = \mathbf{a}_{sp_i}^{(VC)}|_P + \mathbf{a}_{sp_i}^{(VC)}|_I + \mathbf{a}_{sp_i}^{(VC)}|_D$, where the subscripts ‘P’, ‘I’, and ‘D’ respectively denote the proportional, integral, and derivative contributions. Under the hypothesis of quasi-steady external disturbances, based on the capability of integral contributions to reject external disturbances [38], it is assumed that $\tilde{\mathbf{f}}_{d_i} = -m \mathbf{a}_{sp_i}^{(VC)}|_I$. Hence, estimated input force is given as $\hat{\mathbf{u}}_i = \mathbf{T}_{BE}^T(\tilde{\boldsymbol{\eta}}_i)[0, 0, -\tilde{T}_i]^T - m \mathbf{a}_{sp_i}^{(VC)}|_I$.

4.4. Performance indicators

Indicators are defined to characterize the performance of the closed-loop system with and without the auxiliary support of PC.

- Maneuver time, t_m . It is the total time required to conclude a prescribed maneuver, based on a stop criterion. Define $\delta_i = [\delta_{x_i}, \delta_{y_i}, \delta_{z_i}]^T = \tilde{\mathbf{d}}_i - \mathbf{d}_i$ and $\epsilon_i = [\epsilon_{x_i}, \epsilon_{y_i}, \epsilon_{z_i}]^T = \mathbf{v}_r - \mathbf{v}_i$ as the relative position and trajectory error variables, respectively. The simulation starts at $t = 0$ s and is assumed to be concluded when two conditions are simultaneously satisfied: 1) the formation control residual error $e_r = \left\| [\delta_1^T \epsilon_1^T \delta_2^T \epsilon_2^T]^T \right\|$ falls below 0.2, provided δ_i and ϵ_i are expressed in m and m/s, respectively, and 2) the absolute value of ζ remains bounded below 0.5 deg for a prescribed time of 5 s.
- Average swing angle, ζ_{av} . It is calculated as $\zeta_{av} = I_\zeta(t_m)/t_m$ where the integral

$$I_\zeta(t_m) = \int_0^{t_m} |\zeta(s)| ds \quad (42)$$

is evaluated over maneuver time interval and provides an indication of how much and how long payload position P_l remains far from the local vertical plane Γ .

- Total propulsive energy, E_{prop} . It is the mechanical energy delivered by electrical motors to propellers, calculated by the integral

$$E_{prop} = \int_0^{t_m} \sum_{j=1}^8 P_{sh_j}(s) ds \quad (43)$$

where $P_{sh_j} = Q_j \Omega_j$ is the output shaft power generated by the j -th motor, $j = 1, \dots, 8$, obtained from required torque Q_j and angular rate Ω_j under the assumption of null friction torque. In the present case, E_{prop} is calculated for Agent 1 only.

4.5. Test cases

Consider the desired formation identified by $\tilde{\boldsymbol{\gamma}} = [0, 10, 0]^T$ m. It follows $\tilde{\mathbf{d}}_1 = -\tilde{\mathbf{d}}_2 = [0, 5, 0]^T$ m, provided $\tilde{\gamma}_x = 0$ m and $\tilde{\gamma}_y = 10$ m. Since $\tilde{\boldsymbol{\gamma}} = \|\tilde{\boldsymbol{\gamma}}\| < 2L = 15$ m, the designed formation is well-posed according to Remark 2 (in this case $\tilde{\boldsymbol{\gamma}}^* = 2L \sqrt{1 + m_l/(2m)} \approx 39.28$ m).

The first simulation case (‘1’) is described to validate the formation acquisition capabilities and the payload mass estimation method discussed in Theorem 1 and Remark 1 while $\mathbf{a}_{sp_i}^{(PC)} = \mathbf{0}$ m/s². The octarotors are required to leave the initial state defined at $t = 0$ s by $\mathbf{r}_1(0) = [2, 5.2, -18]^T$ m, $\mathbf{r}_2(0) = [-4, -5.2, -18]^T$ m, and $\mathbf{v}_1(0) = \mathbf{v}_2(0) = [0, 0, 0]^T$ m/s, with $\zeta(0) = 3.6$ deg and $\dot{\zeta}(0) = 0$ deg/s. The initial attitude is represented by $\boldsymbol{\eta}_1(0) = -\boldsymbol{\eta}_2(0) = [8.89, -5.19, 0]$ deg. The reference point is a constant, $\mathbf{r}_r(t) = [0, 0, -20]^T$ m, and the desired yaw angle is $\psi_{sp_1} = \psi_{sp_2} = 0$ deg. The maneuver is performed in the presence of a constant wind $\mathbf{w} = [-2, 1.5, 0]^T$ m/s, with components expressed in \mathcal{F}_E . During the maneuver, performed with a prescribed 60 s duration, Eq. (19) is solved on board Vehicle 1 and the solution $\hat{m}_l = (-b_1 + \sqrt{b_1^2 - 4a_1c_1})/(2a_1)$ is considered. In Fig. 6.a, the residual error e_r is plotted as a function of time, showing correct stabilization of formation geometry. In Fig. 6.b, the estimated payload mass is reported, provided a low-pass filter is applied to the computed value, as obtained by a first-order transfer function with time constant $\tau_{LP} = 0.5$ s. After a rapid initial transient ($t \leq 2$ s), the algorithm reaches plausible values and stabilizes to a steady-state solution. By averaging the last 10

Fig. 7. Case 1: comparison between real and estimated control forces.

Fig. 8. Case 1: comparison between real and estimated disturbance forces.

s of data, one has $\hat{m}_l = 99.76$ kg, which infers satisfactory accuracy. It is noted that mass estimation error (-0.24%) accounts for the presence of a hook point that is distinct from vehicle's center of gravity, which goes against the hypotheses at the basis of proposed algorithms (and is responsible for the high-frequency oscillations in Figs. 6–8). The estimation of control and disturbance forces plays a fundamental role, as it was pointed out in Remarks 1 and 3. In this respect, Figs. 7 and 8 report a comparison between real and estimated values for Vehicle 1, which reaches the steady-state measured attitude identified by $\bar{\phi}_1 = 7.88$ deg, $\bar{\theta}_1 = -0.71$ deg, and $\bar{\alpha}_1 = \arccos(\cos \bar{\phi}_1 \cos \bar{\theta}_1) = 7.91$ deg. During the maneuver, payload oscillation is excited according to Fig. 9, until the rest condition is practically acquired. The system results to be evidently underdamped, provided dissipative effects are (directly) generated by payload aerodynamic drag and (indirectly) by the stabilization of formation speed errors, ϵ_1 and ϵ_2 .

The second maneuver ('2') is adopted as a test case to perform filter tuning, based on payload mass value \hat{m}_l estimated above. The octaro-

tors leave the initial state defined by $\mathbf{r}_1(0) = [0, 5, -20]^T$ m, $\mathbf{r}_2(0) = [0, -5, -20]^T$ m, and $\mathbf{v}_1(0) = \mathbf{v}_2(0) = [0, 0, 0]^T$ m/s, with the payload at rest in the absence of wind. The initial attitude is $\boldsymbol{\eta}_1(0) = -\boldsymbol{\eta}_2(0) = [8.38, 0, 0]^T$ deg. The reference point is a constant, $\mathbf{r}_r(t) = [20, 0, -20]^T$ m, and the desired yaw angle is $\psi_{sp1} = \psi_{sp2} = 0$ deg. Dynamic system matrices in Eqs. (27) and (28) are, respectively:

$$\mathbf{A}_\zeta = \begin{bmatrix} 0 & 1 \\ -1.1876 & 0 \end{bmatrix}, \quad \mathbf{B}_\zeta = \begin{bmatrix} 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 \\ -0.5051 & 0 & 0 & -0.5051 & 0 & 0 \end{bmatrix} \cdot 10^{-3} \quad (44)$$

The state-transition matrix is computed by Matlab[®] matrix exponential function $\text{expm}(\cdot)$, according to the method in [39]:

$$\boldsymbol{\Phi} = \begin{bmatrix} 0.9999 & 0.010 \\ -0.0119 & 0.9999 \end{bmatrix} \quad (45)$$

The control-input model is:

Fig. 9. Case 1: stabilization of swing angle and rate.

Fig. 10. Case 2: (a) formation error stabilization and (b) estimation convergence for the nominal covariance matrix.

$$\Gamma = \begin{bmatrix} -0.0025 & 0 & 0 & -0.0025 & 0 & 0 \\ -0.5051 & 0 & 0 & -0.5051 & 0 & 0 \end{bmatrix} \cdot 10^{-5} \quad (46)$$

For the sake of brevity, the tuning and scaling procedures detailed in [29] to find the globally-optimum FGDF configuration are not described. Final results are directly provided, where $\beta = 0.998$ is the best fading factor at which the estimated measurement noise covariance matrix \tilde{R} satisfies $\tilde{R} = R^* \approx R$, where R^* and R are, respectively, the assigned and the true noise covariance values. In the present case $R = 1.98 \cdot 10^{-5} \text{ rad}^2$ and the assigned value is $R^* = 1.95 \cdot 10^{-5} \text{ rad}^2$. The algorithm is initialized with null state vector and nominal error covariance $(E^-)^{(0)} = \text{diag}(8, 9) \cdot 10^{-8}$. The time history of formation residual e_r in the case when $a_{sp_i}^{(PC)} = 0 \text{ m/s}^2$ is reported in Fig. 10.a, provided that maneuver time is $t_m = 71.2 \text{ s}$. Filter stabilization occurs as in Fig. 10.b, where the trace of the nominal covariance matrix E (and, therefore, the gain of the estimator) sets on a constant value. With respect to filter performance, a comparison is reported in Fig. 11 between the true, the filter-estimated, and the measured oscillation angle according to

Table 2

Case 2: summary of performance indicators.

index	without PC	with PC	error [%]
t_m [s]	71.2	42.1	-40.9
$I_\zeta(t_m)$ [deg s]	299.71	172.03	-42.6
ζ_{av} [deg]	4.21	4.08	-3.1
E_{prop} [kJ]	995.7	589.6	-40.8

Eq. (33). In Fig. 12 satisfactory performance of the recursive algorithm is assessed also for the estimation of oscillation rate.

In the case when PC is activated according to Eq. (41), based on the feedback of estimated variables, the same maneuver is concluded with $t_m = 42.1 \text{ s}$. The beneficial effect of $a_{sp_i}^{(PC)}$ is also evident in Fig. 13, where oscillation variables are shown to be rapidly damped. With respect to other performance indicators, Table 2 summarizes main results and computes percentage errors. It is noteworthy that a 40.8% reduction of required energy is obtained thanks to PC strategy.

Fig. 11. Case 2: comparison between the real, the measured, and the estimated oscillation angle.

Fig. 12. Case 2: comparison between the real and the estimated oscillation rate.

In the last simulation case ('3') the octarotors start from a hovering condition characterized by $\mathbf{r}_1(0) = [2, 0, -20]^T$ m and $\mathbf{r}_2(0) = [-2, 0, -20]^T$ m with the payload at rest in the presence of steady wind $\mathbf{w} = [-0.5, 2, -1]^T$ m/s. Desired formation geometry and FGDF equations are reconfigured with $\bar{\mathbf{y}} = [4, 0, 0]^T$ m and null set-point yaw angles. The tuning, scaling, and initialization parameters given above for the estimation algorithm are left unchanged to validate filter configuration robustness with respect to (at least bounded) formation geometry variations. Reference trajectory is defined by $\mathbf{r}_r(t) = [t, 2, -20]^T$ m ($\mathbf{v}_r(t) = [1, 0, 0]^T$ m/s) for $t < 20$ s and $\mathbf{r}_r(t) = [2t - 20, 0, -20]^T$ m ($\mathbf{v}_r(t) = [2, 0, 0]^T$ m/s) for $t \geq 20$ s. An additive disturbance signal $\mathbf{a}_{sp1}^{(D)} = [-3, 0, 0]^T$ m/s² is assumed to perturb Eq. (37) for $i = 1$ during time interval $30 \leq t \leq 31$ s, thus simulating a short-term malfunction of control system in Agent 1. Provided the focus is posed on speed tracking capabilities, Condition 1 in Sec. 4.4, that defines maneuver time, is here adapted to the reduced-order speed error $e_{rs} = \left\| \begin{bmatrix} \epsilon_1^T \\ \epsilon_2^T \end{bmatrix} \right\|$, required to fall below 0.02 m/s. Fig. 14.a reports the time history of error $e_\gamma = \|\bar{\mathbf{y}} - \boldsymbol{\gamma}\|$, showing stabilization of close formation for $R_{sph} = 1$ m.

Table 3

Case 3: summary of performance indicators.

index	without PC	with PC	error [%]
t_m [s]	60.4	44.8	-25.7
$I_\zeta(t_m)$ [deg s]	62.60	34.76	-44.5
ζ_{av} [deg]	1.04	0.78	-25.2
E_{prop} [kJ]	845.6	630.5	-25.4

The beneficial effect of CAC is evident during time interval $30 \leq t \leq 31$ s (see gray areas), where safety margin with respect to eventual collision is guaranteed. In Fig. 14.b, the speed error e_{rs} is plotted with satisfactory accuracy of the speed-tracking capabilities. Table 3 resumes main indicator values with evident advantages of the proposed estimation and control strategy, especially in terms of required energy and maneuver time. Finally, Fig. 15 depicts the true oscillation angle and rate as obtained with and without PC, showing reduced swing in the former case.

Fig. 13. Case 2: stabilization of oscillation (a) angle and (b) rate with and without PC.

Fig. 14. Case 3: stabilization of (a) formation geometry and (b) residual speed error with PC.

5. Conclusions

The cooperative transportation of a payload using two identical rotorcraft was investigated. The system, comprising three point masses connected by two rigid, massless cables and subject to external disturbances, was first modeled through a Lagrangian formulation. The resulting equations of motion were subsequently linearized around a hovering equilibrium in which the payload remains stationary. These equations were then reformulated to enable estimation of the payload's swing state (specifically, its angle and angular rate), based on measurements of the vehicles' accelerations in the inertial frame. To this end, a recursive estimation algorithm known as the Fading Gaussian Deterministic Filter was employed.

The proposed methodology was validated numerically within a high-fidelity simulation environment involving heavy-lift octarotors tasked with maintaining formation geometry, following prescribed trajectories, and avoiding inter-agent collisions. The estimated swing states were integrated into a closed-loop feedback control scheme designed for active

stabilization of the payload. A practical implementation strategy was also outlined, leveraging commercially available autopilot systems. Results demonstrated that the inclusion of swing state feedback not only enhances delivery accuracy but also leads to reductions in maneuver time and energy consumption across a range of operational scenarios.

CRedit authorship contribution statement

Elia Costantini: Writing – review & editing, Validation, Software, Resources, Methodology, Investigation, Formal analysis, Data curation, Conceptualization. **Emanuele L. de Angelis:** Writing – review & editing, Writing – original draft, Visualization, Validation, Supervision, Software, Resources, Project administration, Methodology, Investigation, Funding acquisition, Formal analysis, Data curation, Conceptualization. **Fabrizio Giulietti:** Writing – review & editing, Visualization, Validation, Supervision, Resources, Project administration, Funding acquisition, Formal analysis, Data curation.

Fig. 15. Case 3: stabilization of oscillation (a) angle and (b) rate with and without PC.

Declaration of competing interest

The authors declare the following financial interests/personal relationships which may be considered as potential competing interests: Emanuele Luigi de Angelis reports financial support was provided by European Union. If there are other authors, they declare that they have no known competing financial interests or personal relationships that could have affected or influenced the work reported in this paper.

Acknowledgements

This study was carried out within the MOST - Sustainable Mobility National Research Center and received funding from the European Union Next-GenerationEU (PIANO NAZIONALE DI RIPRESA E RESILIENZA (PNRR) - MISSIONE 4 COMPONENTE 2, INVESTIMENTO 1.4 - D.D. 1033 17/06/2022, CN00000023). This manuscript reflects only the authors' views and opinions, neither the European Union nor the European Commission can be considered responsible for them.

Appendix A. Proof of Theorem 1

The angle $\bar{\alpha}_i > 0$ between $-z_E$ and the i -th equilibrium control force \bar{f}_{c_i} is given by:

$$\tan \bar{\alpha}_i = -\frac{\sqrt{\bar{f}_{x_{c_i}}^2 + \bar{f}_{y_{c_i}}^2}}{\bar{f}_{z_{c_i}}} \quad (47)$$

After squaring both members of Eq. (47) and taking into account Eqs. (17) and (18), one has:

$$\left(\frac{g m_i \xi_i \bar{\gamma}_x}{2\sqrt{4L^2 - \bar{\gamma}^2}} - \bar{f}_{x_{d_i}} \right)^2 + \left(\frac{g m_i \xi_i \bar{\gamma}_y}{2\sqrt{4L^2 - \bar{\gamma}^2}} - \bar{f}_{y_{d_i}} \right)^2 - \left(-\frac{gM}{2} - \bar{f}_{z_{d_i}} \right)^2 \tan^2 \bar{\alpha}_i = 0 \quad (48)$$

Since $\xi_i^2 = 1$ and $\bar{\gamma}^2 = \bar{\gamma}_x^2 + \bar{\gamma}_y^2$, Eq. (48) is finally manipulated to obtain the polynomial expression in Eq. (16), where payload mass m_i is collected. In the case when the agents of the formation are multirotors, \bar{f}_{c_i} is directed along z_{B_i} , such that $\cos \bar{\alpha}_i$ represents the element with position (3, 3) of the direction cosine matrix $T_{BE}(\bar{\eta}_i)$ defined in Sec. 2.1. For the selected attitude representation, irrespective of set-point yaw

angle $\bar{\psi}_i$, it is $\cos \bar{\alpha}_i = \cos \bar{\phi}_i \cos \bar{\theta}_i$, where $\bar{\phi}_i$ and $\bar{\theta}_i$ are the equilibrium roll and pitch angles, respectively [22].

Appendix B. Elements of matrices A and B

In what follows, the elements of matrices **A** and **B** respectively defined in Eqs. (25) and (26) are listed.

$$A_{8,1} = -\frac{g m_i (2 M L^2 - m \bar{\gamma}_y^2)}{2 m (2 M L^2 - m \bar{\gamma}^2) \sqrt{4 L^2 - \bar{\gamma}^2}} = -A_{8,4} = -A_{11,1} = A_{11,4} \quad (49)$$

$$A_{8,2} = -\frac{g m_i \bar{\gamma}_x \bar{\gamma}_y}{2 (2 M L^2 - m \bar{\gamma}^2) \sqrt{4 L^2 - \bar{\gamma}^2}} = -A_{8,5} = A_{9,1} = -A_{11,2} = A_{11,5} = -A_{12,1} = A_{12,4} \quad (50)$$

$$A_{8,3} = -\frac{g m_i^2 \bar{\gamma}_x L^2}{m \bar{\gamma}^2 (2 m_i L^2 + m \bar{\gamma}^2)} = -A_{8,6} = A_{11,3} = -A_{11,6} \quad (51)$$

$$A_{8,7} = \frac{g m_i \bar{\gamma}_y}{2 m \bar{\gamma}} = A_{11,7} \quad (52)$$

$$A_{9,2} = -\frac{g m_i (2 M L^2 - m \bar{\gamma}_x^2)}{2 m (2 M L^2 - m \bar{\gamma}^2) \sqrt{4 L^2 - \bar{\gamma}^2}} = -A_{9,5} = -A_{12,2} = A_{12,5} \quad (53)$$

$$A_{9,3} = -\frac{g m_i^2 \bar{\gamma}_y L^2}{m \bar{\gamma}^2 (2 m_i L^2 + m \bar{\gamma}^2)} = -A_{9,6} = A_{12,3} = -A_{12,6} \quad (54)$$

$$A_{9,7} = -\frac{g m_i \bar{\gamma}_x}{2 m \bar{\gamma}} = A_{12,7} \quad (55)$$

$$A_{10,1} = -\frac{g m_i^2 \bar{\gamma}_x L^2}{m (4 L^2 - \bar{\gamma}^2) (2 M L^2 - m \bar{\gamma}^2)} = -A_{10,4} = A_{13,1} = -A_{13,4} \quad (56)$$

$$A_{10,2} = -\frac{g m_i^2 \bar{\gamma}_y L^2}{m (4 L^2 - \bar{\gamma}^2) (2 M L^2 - m \bar{\gamma}^2)} = -A_{10,5} = A_{13,2} = -A_{13,5} \quad (57)$$

$$A_{10,3} = -\frac{g m_i M L^2}{m (2 m_i L^2 + m \bar{\gamma}^2) \sqrt{4 L^2 - \bar{\gamma}^2}} = -A_{10,6} = -A_{13,3} = A_{13,6} \quad (58)$$

$$A_{10,7} = 0 = A_{13,7} = A_{14,1} = A_{14,2} = A_{14,3} = A_{14,4} = A_{14,5} = A_{14,6} \quad (59)$$

$$A_{14,7} = -\frac{gM}{m\sqrt{4L^2 - \bar{\gamma}^2}} \quad (60)$$

$$B_{8,1} = \frac{1}{m} - \frac{m_l(m+m_l)L^2\bar{\gamma}_x^2}{m[4m_lML^4 + m^2\bar{\gamma}^2(4L^2 - \bar{\gamma}^2)]} = B_{11,4} \quad (61)$$

$$B_{8,2} = -\frac{m_l(m+m_l)L^2\bar{\gamma}_x\bar{\gamma}_y}{m[4m_lML^4 + m^2\bar{\gamma}^2(4L^2 - \bar{\gamma}^2)]} = B_{9,1} = B_{11,5} = B_{12,4} \quad (62)$$

$$B_{8,3} = \frac{m_l(m+m_l)L^2\bar{\gamma}_x\sqrt{4L^2 - \bar{\gamma}^2}}{m[4m_lML^4 + m^2\bar{\gamma}^2(4L^2 - \bar{\gamma}^2)]} = B_{10,1} = -B_{11,6} = -B_{13,4} \quad (63)$$

$$B_{8,4} = -\frac{m_l\bar{\gamma}_x^2(2L^2 - \bar{\gamma}^2)}{2[4m_lML^4 + m^2\bar{\gamma}^2(4L^2 - \bar{\gamma}^2)]} = B_{11,1} \quad (64)$$

$$B_{8,5} = -\frac{m_l\bar{\gamma}_x\bar{\gamma}_y(2L^2 - \bar{\gamma}^2)}{2[4m_lML^4 + m^2\bar{\gamma}^2(4L^2 - \bar{\gamma}^2)]} = B_{9,4} = B_{11,2} = B_{12,1} \quad (65)$$

$$B_{8,6} = -\frac{m_l\bar{\gamma}_x(2L^2 - \bar{\gamma}^2)\sqrt{4L^2 - \bar{\gamma}^2}}{2[4m_lML^4 + m^2\bar{\gamma}^2(4L^2 - \bar{\gamma}^2)]} \quad (66)$$

$$= -B_{10,4} = -B_{11,3} = B_{13,1}$$

$$B_{9,2} = \frac{1}{m} - \frac{m_l(m+m_l)L^2\bar{\gamma}_y^2}{m[4m_lML^4 + m^2\bar{\gamma}^2(4L^2 - \bar{\gamma}^2)]} = B_{12,5} \quad (67)$$

$$B_{9,3} = \frac{m_l(m+m_l)L^2\bar{\gamma}_y\sqrt{4L^2 - \bar{\gamma}^2}}{m[4m_lML^4 + m^2\bar{\gamma}^2(4L^2 - \bar{\gamma}^2)]} = B_{10,2} = -B_{12,6} = -B_{13,5} \quad (68)$$

$$B_{9,5} = -\frac{m_l\bar{\gamma}_y^2(2L^2 - \bar{\gamma}^2)}{2[4m_lML^4 + m^2\bar{\gamma}^2(4L^2 - \bar{\gamma}^2)]} = B_{12,2} \quad (69)$$

$$B_{9,6} = -\frac{m_l\bar{\gamma}_y(2L^2 - \bar{\gamma}^2)\sqrt{4L^2 - \bar{\gamma}^2}}{2[4m_lML^4 + m^2\bar{\gamma}^2(4L^2 - \bar{\gamma}^2)]} \quad (70)$$

$$= -B_{10,5} = -B_{12,3} = B_{13,2}$$

$$B_{10,3} = \frac{1}{m} - \frac{m_l(m+m_l)L^2(4L^2 - \bar{\gamma}^2)}{m[4m_lML^4 + m^2\bar{\gamma}^2(4L^2 - \bar{\gamma}^2)]} = B_{13,6} \quad (71)$$

$$B_{10,6} = \frac{m_l(2L^2 - \bar{\gamma}^2)(4L^2 - \bar{\gamma}^2)}{2[4m_lML^4 + m^2\bar{\gamma}^2(4L^2 - \bar{\gamma}^2)]} = B_{13,3} \quad (72)$$

$$B_{14,1} = -\frac{\bar{\gamma}_y}{m\bar{\gamma}\sqrt{4L^2 - \bar{\gamma}^2}} = B_{14,4} \quad (73)$$

$$B_{14,2} = \frac{\bar{\gamma}_x}{m\bar{\gamma}\sqrt{4L^2 - \bar{\gamma}^2}} = B_{14,5} \quad (74)$$

$$B_{14,3} = B_{14,6} = 0 \quad (75)$$

Data availability

Data will be made available on request.

References

- [1] J. Estevez, G. Garate, J.M. Lopez-Guede, M. Larrea, Review of aerial transportation of suspended-cable payloads with quadrotors, *Drones* 8 (35) (2024) 1–21, <https://doi.org/10.3390/drones8020035>.
- [2] H. Chen, F. Quan, L. Fang, S. Zhang, Aerial grasping with a lightweight manipulator based on multi-objective optimization and visual compensation, *Sensors* 19 (2019) 4253, <https://doi.org/10.3390/s19194253>.
- [3] H. Eskandaripour, E. Boltsaikhon, Last-mile drone delivery: past, present, and future, *Drones* 7 (2) (2023) 1–19, <https://doi.org/10.3390/drones7020077>.
- [4] X. Li, J. Zhang, J. Han, Trajectory planning of load transportation with multi-quadrotors based on reinforcement learning algorithm, *Aerosp. Sci. Technol.* 116 (2021) 106887, <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.ast.2021.106887>.

- [5] E.L. de Angelis, F. Giuliatti, Stability and control issues of multirotor suspended load transportation: an analytical closed-form approach, *Aerosp. Sci. Technol.* 135 (2023) 108201, <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.ast.2023.108201>.
- [6] C. Meissen, K. Klausen, M. Arcaç, T.I. Fossen, A. Packard, Passivity-based formation control for UAVs with a suspended load, *IFAC-PapersOnLine* 50 (1) (2017) 13150–13155, <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.ifacol.2017.08.2169>.
- [7] K. Klausen, C. Meissen, T.I. Fossen, M. Arcaç, T.A. Johansen, Cooperative control for multirotors transporting an unknown suspended load under environmental disturbances, *IEEE Trans. Control Syst. Technol.* 28 (2) (2018) 653–660, <https://doi.org/10.1109/TCST.2018.2876518>.
- [8] M. Tognon, C. Gabellieri, L. Pallottino, A. Franchi, Aerial co-manipulation with cables: the role of internal force for equilibria, stability, and passivity, *IEEE Robot. Autom.* 3 (3) (2018) 2577–2583, <https://doi.org/10.1109/LRA.2018.2803811>.
- [9] I.H.B. Pizetta, A.S. Brandão, M. Sarcinelli-Filho, Avoiding obstacles in cooperative load transportation, *ISA Trans.* 91 (2019) 253–261, <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.isatra.2019.01.019>.
- [10] E. Costantini, E.L. de Angelis, F. Giuliatti, Cooperative transportation of a cable-suspended load using rotorcraft: a minimal swing approach, in: *Proc. of 49th European Rotorcraft Forum*, 2023, pp. 1–14.
- [11] C. Masone, H.H. Bühlhoff, P. Stegagno, Cooperative transportation of a payload using quadrotors: a reconfigurable cable-driven parallel robot, in: *Proc. of IEEE Int. Conf. Intell. Robot. Syst.*, 2016, pp. 1623–1630.
- [12] J. Gimenez, D.C. Gandolfo, L.R. Salinas, C. Rosales, R. Carelli, Multi-objective control for cooperative payload transport with rotorcraft UAVs, *ISA Trans.* 80 (2018) 491–502, <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.isatra.2018.05.022>.
- [13] B. Shirani, M. Najafi, I. Izadi, Cooperative load transportation using multiple UAVs, *Aerosp. Sci. Technol.* 84 (2019) 158–169, <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.ast.2018.10.027>.
- [14] J. Geng, J.W. Langelaan, Cooperative transport of a slung load using load-leading control, *J. Guid. Control Dyn.* 43 (7) (2020) 1313–1331, <https://doi.org/10.2514/1.G004680>.
- [15] R. Azzam, I. Boiko, Y. Zweiri, Swarm cooperative navigation using centralized training and decentralized execution, *Drones* 7 (3) (2023) 193, <https://doi.org/10.3390/drones7030193>.
- [16] S. Lupashin, M. Hehn, M.W. Mueller, A.P. Schoellig, M. Sherback, R.S. D'Andrea, A platform for aerial robotics research and demonstration: the flying machine arena, *Mechatronics* 24 (1) (2014) 41–54, <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.mechatronics.2013.11.006>.
- [17] M. Zürn, K. Morton, A. Heckmann, A. McFadyen, S. Notter, F. Gonzalez, MPC controlled multirotor with suspended slung load: system architecture and visual load detection, in: *Proc. of IEEE Aerospace Conference*, 2016, pp. 1–11.
- [18] T. Chen, J. Shan, A novel cable-suspended quadrotor transportation system: from theory to experiment, *Aerosp. Sci. Technol.* 104 (2020) 105974, <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.ast.2020.105974>.
- [19] Y.S. Kim, K.S. Hong, S.K. Sul, Anti-sway control of container cranes: inclinometer, observer, and state feedback, *Int. J. Control Autom. Syst.* 2 (4) (2004) 435–449, <https://doi.org/10.1.1.454.9911>.
- [20] H. Paul, K. Ono, R. Ladig, K. Shimonomura, A multirotor platform employing a three-axis vertical articulated robotic arm for aerial manipulation tasks, in: *Proc. of IEEE/ASME International Conference on Advanced Intelligent Mechatronics (AIM)*, 2018, pp. 478–485.
- [21] X. Dang, X. Yin, Y. Zhang, C. Gao, J. Wu, Y. Liu, Improved medium baseline RTK positioning performance based on BDS/Galileo/GPS triple-frequency-only observations, *Remote Sens.* 15 (21) (2023) 5198, <https://doi.org/10.3390/rs15215198>.
- [22] E.L. de Angelis, F. Giuliatti, An improved method for swing state estimation in multirotor slung load applications, *Drones* 7 (11) (2023) 654, <https://doi.org/10.3390/drones7110654>.
- [23] M.A. Santos, B.S. Rego, G.V. Raffo, A. Ferramosca, Suspended load path tracking control strategy using a tilt-rotor UAV, *J. Adv. Transp.* 2017 (1) (2017) 1–22, <https://doi.org/10.1155/2017/9095324>.
- [24] B.S. Rego, G.V. Raffo, Suspended load path tracking control using a tilt-rotor UAV based on zonotopic state estimation, *J. Franklin Inst.* 356 (4) (2019) 1695–1729, <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jfranklin.2018.08.028>.
- [25] G. Li, A. Tunchez, G. Loianno, PCMPC: perception-constrained model predictive control for quadrotors with suspended loads using a single camera and IMU, in: *Proc. of 2021 IEEE International Conference on Robotics and Automation (ICRA)*, 2021, pp. 2012–2018.
- [26] B. Wang, Z. Ma, S. Lai, L. Zhao, Neural moving horizon estimation for robust flight control, *IEEE Trans. Robot.* 40 (2024) 639–659, <https://doi.org/10.1109/TRO.2023.3331064>.
- [27] A. Jin, C. Li, Q. Wang, Y. Liu, P. Huang, F. Zhang, Neural predictor for flight control with payload, *IEEE Robot. Autom. Lett.* 10 (7) (2025) 7055–7062, <https://doi.org/10.1109/LRA.2025.3573624>.
- [28] E.L. de Angelis, G. Ferrarese, F. Giuliatti, D. Modenini, P. Tortora, Terminal height estimation using a fading Gaussian deterministic filter, *Aerosp. Sci. Technol.* 55 (2016) 366–376, <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.ast.2016.06.013>.
- [29] E.L. de Angelis, Swing angle estimation for multicopter slung load applications, *Aerosp. Sci. Technol.* 89 (2019) 264–274, <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.ast.2019.04.014>.

- [30] E.L. de Angelis, F. Giulietti, G. Rossetti, Multirotor aircraft formation flight control with collision avoidance capability, *Aerosp. Sci. Technol.* 77 (2018) 733–741, <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.ast.2018.04.002>.
- [31] P. Outeiro, C. Cardeira, P. Oliveira, Control architecture for a quadrotor transporting a cable-suspended load of uncertain mass, *Drones* 7 (3) (2023) 201, <https://doi.org/10.3390/drones7030201>.
- [32] PX4 Development Team and Community, PX4 autopilot user guide, <https://docs.px4.io/main/en/>, 2024. (Accessed 16 April 2024).
- [33] A.H.J. de Ruiter, C.J. Damaren, J.R. Forbes, *Spacecraft Dynamics and Control - an Introduction*, John Wiley & Sons, Ltd., Sussex, 2013, pp. 19–24.
- [34] T. Li, H. Xing, E. Hashemi, H.D. Taghirad, M. Tavakoli, A brief survey of observers for disturbance estimation and compensation, *Robotica* 41 (12) (2023) 3818–3845, <https://doi.org/10.1017/S0263574723001091>.
- [35] J.C. Butcher, Numerical methods for ordinary differential equations in the 20th century, *J. Comput. Appl. Math.* 125 (2000) 1–29, [https://doi.org/10.1016/S0377-0427\(00\)00455-6](https://doi.org/10.1016/S0377-0427(00)00455-6).
- [36] U.S. Government Printing Office, U.S. Standard Atmosphere, NOAA-S/T 76-1562, Washington, D.C., 1976.
- [37] Defense Mapping Agency Washington DC, Department of Defense World Geodetic System 1984: Its Definition and Relationships with Local Geodetic Systems, 2nd edition, Washington, D.C., 1991.
- [38] S. Ogawa, Robust PID controller tuning for input disturbance rejection, *IFAC Proc.* Vol. 30 (9) (1997) 295–300, [https://doi.org/10.1016/S1474-6670\(17\)43171-5](https://doi.org/10.1016/S1474-6670(17)43171-5).
- [39] N.J. Higham, The scaling and squaring method for the matrix exponential revisited, *SIAM J. Matrix Anal. Appl.* 26 (4) (2005) 1179–1193, <https://doi.org/10.1137/04061101X>.